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Research Article

MICROSTRUCTURAL ALTERATIONS IN THE LYMPHOID ORGANS OF THE PERIADOLESCENT RATS AFTER EXPERIMENTAL EXPOSURE TO THE REPEATED AND VARIABLE STRESSORS.

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Abstract:

Recent investigations demonstrated that chronic variable stressors exhibit more severe effect on the endocrine and immune systems of the body compared the repeating stressors. During adolescent period of life lymphoid organs undergo fast developmental changes which may overlap with stress-induced immunomodulation. The influence of different chronically applied stressors on the lymphoid organs during various phases of periadolescence requires further investigation.

The objective of this research is to evaluate immunomodulatory effect of variable vs. repeating stressors on the morphology of the lymphoid organs in periadolescent experimental animals of different age.

Repeating or variable stressors were applied for 9 days continuously to the infant and early pubertal rats. Central (thymus) and peripheral (spleen) lymphoid organs were sampled and evaluated using morphometry of the immunologically stained histological sections.

Chronic variable stressors exposure showed more significant immunosuppressive effect in the thymus and spleen of the infant rats compared to the early pubertal ones, as demonstrated by more significant decrease of the volume density of different populations of immunocytes in the thymus and the spleen, and an increase of the density of caspase-3-positive cells in the spleen. Comparative evaluation of the repeating stressor exposure revealed significant reduction of the volume density of the CD20+ lymphocytes and increased apoptotic rate in the spleen of both age groups; CD45RC+ lymphocytes in the thymus and CD4+, CD8+ and CD90+ cells in the spleen were reduced in the infant rats only, while in early pubertal rats reduction was not significant compared to the control animals.

This microscopic study shows that different neuroendocrine consequences of chronically applied variable vs. repeating stressors during various periods of early age induce complex age-dependent immunomodulation due to the overlapping of the developmental changes and post-stress alterations in the central and peripheral lymphoid organs in the immature body of the experimental animals.

Key words: immune organs, stress, adolescence, immunohistochemistry, morphometry

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INTRODUCTION:

In recent years, immunomodulatory effect of stress was shown in numerous papers [1-10]. Stress-responsiveness is determined by the interplay of the neuroendocrine and sympathetic nervous systems [11]. Stress-induced immunity changes are regulated by different mechanisms, among which the most significant is the effect of the hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal axis hormones on the receptors of the immune cells [12,5,13]. Many researchers demonstrate that chronic stress may suppress immune function of the body and initiate accelerated immunological aging, while short-term stress is usually immuno-enhancing [14,15,10,5,6,8,9].

On the contrary, other investigators provide evidence of immunosuppression after a short-term stress and absence of immunosuppression or even immuno-enhancement in chronic stress [16,17,18,24,12,18,19]. For example, chronic psychosocial stress was shown to induce activation and differentiation of T cells into Th1, Th2, and Th17 effector cells in peripheral lymph nodes; enhance the frequency of regulatory T cells in the CD4 population, the suppressive activity of bone marrow-derived myeloid-derived suppressor cells towards proliferating T cells in the spleen and create inflammatory immune status of the body [16,17]. These controversies may be explained by the complexity of the effect of stress hormones on the immune function of the body and demonstrate that the problem of stress-related immunomodulation is far from being resolved.

Vulnerability of lymphoid tissue to stress depends not only on the type of stress (acute or chronic with various stress exposure length, physical or psychological, mild or severe, escapable or non-escapable, predictable or non-predictable), but also on the other features which affect responsiveness of the hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal axis, such as age, sex, strain of the experimental animal, history of previous exposure to stressors, as well as the initial immune status of the body. On the contrary to the acute stress, the chronic one is more likely to adversely affect the neuroimmunoendocrine system [1,15,10,5,7].

In spite of all research performed to understand the complications of stress exposure of the body and attempts undertaken to find proper measures of defense, further searches are necessary for clearer understanding of the mechanisms of post-stress changes in the central nervous system, endocrine glands and lymphoid organs. Quite often stress-related impairment of the immunity is assessed using

molecular or immunological methods or even the weight of the immune organs (thymus, spleen) [20,21,2,22,23,8,24]. These methods may evaluate total cell count of lymphoid cells in blood or lymphoid organs [1,3]. As thymus, lymph nodes and spleen are strongly compartmentalized organs, the distribution of different types of target cells between their compartments is very important for the adequate immune response. Very few microstructural research works have been done evaluating alterations in the immune organs after stress exposure. Some researchers assess various compartments in the lymphoid organs without evaluation of distribution of the immune cells among them and consideration of the crosstalk between different types of lymphocytes [25,4,9,26].

Early life stress may have severe consequences for the body, including dysregulation of the hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal axis and increased overall risk on psychopathology [27]. Although various aspects of post-stress immunomodulation has been studied widely in different age groups [12,13,26,19], detailed stress-induced alterations in the lymphoid organs during early life need to be further elaborated. In few papers on stress-induced morphological changes in the immune system of the immature body, the correlation between developmental and stress-induced alterations in the lymphoid organs is not emphasized [20,4,23,9,24].

Recently, some papers described consequences of exposure to the changing stressors, which become more common these days [20,28,29,9,24]. Changes to the microarchitecture of both central and peripheral lymphoid organs in the immature body exposed to variable stressors at some age deserve more attention for deeper comprehension of their mechanisms and development of the defensive measures.

The objective of this study is to assess the influence of repeating and variable stressors on the microstructure of lymphoid tissue in the primary and secondary immune organs of the periadolescent rats of different age.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Periadolescent Sprague Dawley male rats aged 30 (infant period) and 60 (early pubertal period) days [30] were involved in this study. The design of the project was approved by the ethical committee of the Faculty of Medicine, UiTM, Selangor, Malaysia, protocol ACUC 4-11, 14.04.11.

Each age group included three subgroups of six rats each, making a total of 36 rats. Group 1 served as an age-matched control, Group 2 animals were exposed

to the repeating stressors and Group 3 animals were exposed to variable stressors [31]. Exposure lasted for 9 days with daily 2-hour stress sessions. Control animals were not in contact with the treated animals. After the last stress session, animals were euthanized under anaesthesia. Their thymus and spleen were sampled, processed, embedded in paraffin, sectioned and stained by haematoxylin and eosin. Immunohistochemistry was performed using antibodies against CD4 (clone W3/25, AbDSerotec, US); CD8 (clone MRC OX8, AbDSerotec); CD90 (clone HIS51, BD Biosciences); caspase-3, (AbDSerotec, US); CD20 (clone R1N-9D3, AbDSerotec) and CD45RC (clone OX22, AbDSerotec, US). Streptavidin-biotin-peroxydase was used to identify the end product, according to manufacturer's recommendations. Quantitative data on the distribution of immunoreactivity were obtained using the Image Pro+ 8.0 (Media Cybernetics, US) software.

All data are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M, (n = 6) group. The results were analyzed by one-way

analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Student–Newman–Keuls multiple comparison test; $p < 0.05$ values were considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Both repeating and variable stressors caused microscopic changes in the spleen which included reduction of the volume of the T- and B-zones in the white pulp, marginal zone (MZ), expanded marginal sinus (MS), decreased cellular density in the periarterial lymphoid sheathes (PALS) around the central arteries (CA) and arteries of the white pulp (AWP), and in the lymphoid nodules (LN), increased number of macrophages and megakaryocytes (Mb) in the red pulp (RP) (Fig.1). Microarchitecture of the thymus in both experimental groups was also disrupted, with reduced thickness of the thymic cortex (C), indistinct border between cortex and medulla (M), increased number of tingibile body macrophages (TbM) in the cortex and Hassal's corpuscles in the medulla (Fig.2).

Fig.1. Microphotographs of the spleen of the control (1a,d,g) and experimental (repeating-1b,e,h; variable-1c,f,i) groups of rats; 1a,b,c – infant rats, staining for CD8; 1d,e,f – early pubertal rats, staining for CD90; 1g,h,I infant rats, staining for CD20. Magnification x400 (1a,b,c,d,e,f,i) and x200 (g,h). Legends: MZ – marginal zone, MS – marginal sinus, PALS – periarterial lymphoid sheath, CA – central artery, AWP – artery of the white pulp, LN – lymphoid nodule, Mb – megakaryocyte.

Fig.2. Microphotographs of the thymus of the control (2a) and experimental (repeating – 2b, variable – 2c) groups of infant rats; staining for CD45RC; magnification x400. Legends: C – cortex, M - medulla, TbM -tingible body macrophages

Immunohistochemical staining revealed changes in the distribution of the immunocytes between different compartments of the spleen and thymus. The data of morphometric analysis are presented in Figures 3 to 8.

Fig.3 Volume density of the CD8+cells in the spleen of the control and experimental rats (%), M±m

Fig.4 Volume density of the CD90+cells in the spleen of the control and experimental rats (%), M±m

Fig.5 Volume density of the CD4+cells in the spleen of the control and experimental rats (%), M±m

Fig.6 Volume density of the CD20+cells in the spleen of the control and experimental prepubertal rats (%), M±m

Fig.7. Volume density of the caspase-3+cells in the spleen of the control and experimental rats (%), M±m

Fig.8. Volume density of the CD45RC+cells in the thymus of the control and experimental rats (%), M±m

There was a highly significant reduction of volume density of the CD8+ ($p<0.01$) and CD90+ ($p<0.01$ and $p<0.001$) cells in the variable stress groups of younger and older age subgroups. In the repeating stress group, it was significantly reduced in the younger age subgroup only ($p<0.05$), while in the older subgroup the difference from control group did not reach the level of significance (Figures 3 and 4). In the variable stress group, CD4+ cells in the spleen showed highly significant ($p<0.01$) and significant ($p<0.05$) reductions of volume densities in the younger and older groups respectively. In the repeating stress group, this reduction was significant only in younger rats ($p<0.05$) (Fig.5). CD20-positive cells were significantly reduced in both experimental groups and age subgroups with different levels of significance ($p<0.05$ in the repeating stress group and $p<0.01$ in the variable stress group) (Fig. 6). Caspase-3 positive cells displayed significantly increased volume density ($p<0.05$) in both age subgroups of the repeating stress group. In the heterotypic variable stress group, the difference was significant for the older subgroup ($p<0.05$) and highly significant ($p<0.01$) for the younger age group (Fig.7).

In the thymus, volume density of the CD45RC groups showed highly significant reductions in both younger age stress subgroups ($p<0.01$), while in the older group this difference was significant only in the variable stress group ($p<0.05$) (Fig.8).

DISCUSSION:

Our data are in agreement with the results of other investigators on the immunosuppressive effect of chronic stress with reduced lymphocyte population and antibody production due to stress hormones in the periadolescent animals [20,23,8,24,19], and provide additional information on the apoptotic rate of splenocytes and distribution of different populations of lymphocytes between the compartments of the central and peripheral lymphoid organs in the growing body of the stressed experimental animals. Earlier we reported our data on the changes in the splenic white pulp of the infantile and adolescent rats induced by the homo- and heterotypic stressors, which showed that stress exposure, particularly during the most sensitive period of immunological maturation (preweaning age) causes lymphocyte depletion in the T- and B-zones of the organ, reduction of the number of follicular dendritic cells, inhibition of proliferation of splenocytes and increased apoptotic rate, the severity of which depended on the type of stressors applied [32].

Our current research demonstrated the effect of the repeating and variable stressors on the microarchitecture and intensity of apoptoses in the central (thymus) and peripheral (spleen) organs of the immune system in the infant and early pubertal rats, and altered distribution of different subpopulations of immunocytes between thymic cortex/medulla and splenic white pulp/red pulp/marginal zone.

It has been shown [4,18] that chronic stress increases the mass of the white pulp and its subcompartments and enhances immune reactivity in the animals with the previous early life stress history. Our results show that early life stress has immediate immunosuppressive effect which makes the growing body vulnerable to infections and other adverse events, but once overcome, we presume, it may result in enhanced immunity during stress exposure in adulthood.

On the contrary to the other researchers, who were mainly using immunological and biochemical/molecular methods for the evaluation of the post-stress immune status of the body, we applied histological and immunohistochemical methods which allowed us not only to observe the microscopic alterations in the subcompartments of the central and peripheral immune organs, but also to assess distribution of different population of immunocytes between them. Our results showed that sensitivity to the different types of stress (repeating vs. variable) depends on the particular age within periadolescent period of early life. Different subpopulation of T-cells (CD4+, CD8+, CD90+) were significantly reduced in the younger group of animals subjected to both types of stress exposures. In older rats, this was true only in the variable stress group. Similar patterns of changes were observed in the recirculation pool of lymphocytes, as demonstrated by image analysis of the CD45RC+ cells in the thymic medulla. These changes correspond to the hypothalamo-hypophyseoadrenal system activation patterns in different stress paradigms at early stages of postnatal development [33,34]. On the contrary, B-cell density was significantly reduced in the older rats of both stress groups. This finding indicates different sensitivity to various types of stress of the cells in the B-zones of the spleen in the different age groups. Similarly, the rate of apoptosis was increased in both types of chronic stress in younger and older rats as evidenced by image analysis of the caspase-3+cells. Thus, variable and repeating stress-related immunomodulation in the central and peripheral immune organs shows diverse scopes and ranges at different stages of early postnatal life and proves to

be a result of complex correlations of developmental and post-stress alterations in the body.

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